

The Velvet Underground and their Era-Defining Debut Album

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Abstract: In this article, the emphasis is put on the cultural and social significance centred around the production of *The Velvet Underground and Nico* LP, the notable differences in now and then public's perception of the album, and how their life in New York with all its cultural and social unrest impacted their masterpiece. The release of The Velvet Underground's debut album definitely moulded the rock genre and forever impacted the music industry, representing a paramount source of inspiration for many successors. Lou Reed and co's musical genius significantly marked the 1960s artistic scene and left the world a perfectly raw legacy of the wild New York's rock 'n' roll stage of the late '60s.

Key words: The Velvet Underground, Nico, Andy Warhol, rock, counterculture

The Velvet Underground formed in 1964, consisting of Lou Reed, John Cale, Sterling Morrison, and Mo Tucker, later to be joined by the German singer and actress Nico. The foursome represented the 60s counterculture, their main inspiration being the surreptitious, on edge life of New York, immersed in a community indulged in drugs, sex, and alcohol. Even if they were in their 20s, their musical background was well-defined, showcasing impressive experiences and studies in this area. In the book *Up-tight*, Victor Bockris and Gerard Malanga explain Cale and Reed's artistic differences through their early lives. While John Cale had an academic degree in classical music composition, Lou Reed was struggling with his dyslexia and his parents who wanted him to become a classical pianist. Lou was a 'natural born rock & roll animal'¹ who confronted his family by joining his first band in high school.

Back then, rock music was considered the new generation's political and social liberation, with The Velvet Underground being perceived as the outcasts of this musical revolution. The band's debut album triggered different opinions upon their artistic intentions. In Jeremy Gilbert's perception, The Underground created 'queer rock'² which was a game changer regarding the pop music gender scale and managed to shed light on certain topics that used to be regarded as taboo. However, Dave Thompson states that even though the Velvets were a rock and roll band, their musical underlay was anti-rock. Thompson feels that this obvious paradox reflected band's quintessence, making them become 'the most influential band to come out of white rocking America—ever'.³

Their bizarre and impressive courage to sing about the taboo lifestyle of the East Coast society drew Andy Warhol's attention who wanted to convert his studio into a rock & roll cult: 'They seemed like the perfect fit for Warhol's strange fiefdom, The Factory, devoted to

¹ Victor Bockris and Gerard Malanga, *Up-tight: The Velvet Underground Story*, Updated Edition (London: Music Sales Limited, 2009), pp.13-16.

² Jeremy Gilbert, 'White Light/White Heat: Jouissance beyond Gender in the Velvet Underground', In *Living through Pop*, ed. by Andrew Blake (London: Routledge, 1999), p.43.

³ Dave Thompson, *Alternative Rock* (San Francisco: Miller Freeman, 2000), p.2.

art, debutantes, drag queens, junkies, and societal cast-offs'.⁴ The Factory was Warhol's avant-garde studio in which art had no boundaries. Steven Watson and Nat Finkelstein share the same concept about the artist's nonconformist mindset. The latter considers his studio a place only for 'experimenters' who are always in control of their visions.⁵ Watson also believes that The Factory was about the people and their personalities, rather than the forms of art or any other cultural implications.⁶ These statements reflect Warhol's tendency to search for aesthetic spirits which would create a bona fide environment for experimental art, encouraging newcomers like the Velvets to try innovative things.

Recording the album in just four days under Warhol's guidance and management denoted the Velvets' authentic and immediate passion for unrefined musical content. In the cited Rolling Stone article, the pop artist's role as the producer of the record is perfectly portrayed: besides his lack of artistic involvement, his notoriety and influence inspired the sound engineers to capture the band's raw and independent sound. The artist's trademark is however visible through the record's famous cover, the 'peelable banana' which reflected the band's essence and attitude towards exposure and revelation.

**THE VELVET
UNDERGROUND
& NICO**

Andy Warhol

Photo: <https://www.primevideo.com>

As a semiotic reflection of the band's beliefs, the album was recorded in an obscure and abysmal rehearsal studio in Ludlow Street on the Lower East Side, New York. In a Rolling Stone article, the building is described as barely functional, with dilapidated walls and equipped with only four microphones. A place 'somewhere between reconstruction and demolition'⁷ seems improper for conducting a normal recording session, but this degraded building and its eerie atmosphere matched the band's realm of creation.

⁴ Cary O'Dell, 'The Velvet Underground and Nico', *Library of Congress* <<https://www.loc.gov/static/programs/national-recording-preservation-board/documents/VelvetUnderground.pdf>> [accessed 12 February 2022].

⁵ Nat Finkelstein, *Andy Warhol: the Factory Years 1964-1967* (London: Sidgwick & Jackson Limited, 1989), p.173.

⁶ Steven Watson, *Factory Made: Warhol and the Sixties* (New York: Pantheon Books, 2003), pp.259-260.

⁷ Jordan Runtagh, 'The Velvet Underground and Nico: 10 Things You Didn't Know', *Rolling Stone* (2017) <<https://www.rollingstone.com/feature/the-velvet-underground-and-nico-10-things-you-didnt-know-109041/>> [accessed 15 February 2022].

The Velvet Underground and Nico was released in March 1967. The record was antithetical to Haight-Ashbury's Summer of Love. While The Beatles, Jefferson Airplane, The Mamas & the Papas etc. were thriving through their songs centred around love, peace, and an euphoric state of mind, reaching high positions in the charts, Andy Warhol and his protégés were struggling to break the deadlock. Christoph Grunenberg and Jonathan Harris explain the Underground's failure in San Francisco as the band was 'greeted with derision'⁸ by the aloof, hippie crowd. This event foregrounded the social and cultural implications of the Summer of Love movement which represented a serious impediment for the band to ascend to the next level.

The Velvet Underground's cultural signature represented an opposite approach to the hippie, pop-engulfed West Coast. The record's artistic substance and social implications can be seen throughout Matthew Bannister, Victor Bockris and Gerard Malanga's works. Bannister remarks that *The Velvet Underground and Nico* was a 'reality check', highlighting the main societal differences between the bohemian West Coast and the dark East Coast: 'free love/S&M, West Coast optimism/Eastern cynicism, heterosexuality/homosexuality'.⁹ Similarly, Bockris and Malanga point out the band's repulsion for cloaking the modern reality and its destructive consequences, the intention of their lyrics being to reveal the repugnant truth of the society. When 'hippie rock musicians were infatuated with the spontaneous jam', the Underground dared to write about depravity and drug effects, showing the 'devastating power, horror and false transcendence of heroin addiction'.¹⁰ Thus, we acknowledge the band's cultural reflex of showing the world the other side of the American nation, one more tenebrous than the one that the Californian communities were promoting. Therefore, the band tried to focus more on the society and its controversial issues, rather than the American political scene. In a Guardian article it is outlined the record's surprising lack of political involvement in an event-filled year with Che Guevara's execution, the ongoing Vietnam War, and the race riots in the U.S.¹¹

The record instantly set off controversial opinions. There are substantial differences between the early and nowadays reception. The record did not achieve a commercial success at the time, being poorly promoted, even rejected by the industry and media. In May 1967, the album peaked in at the 171st position in the Billboard chart, never making it to Top 100. There was a disappointing number of copies sold with the record being taken off the shelves quite quickly in June. However, the British musician Brian Eno considers that 'everyone who bought one of those 30,000 copies started a band',¹² helping the Velvets earn their later recognition.

This unfortunate public reception is explained in Joe Harvard and Steven Watson's books in which they see this matter as a fiasco due to the band's business relationship with MGM Records, as well as the bad timing and the subjects tackled in their songs. Harvard considers

⁸ Christoph Grunenberg and Jonathan Harris, *Summer of Love: Psychedelic Art, Social Crisis and Counterculture in the 1960s* (Liverpool: Liverpool University Press, 2005), p.158.

⁹ Matthew Bannister, "'I'm Set Free...': The Velvet Underground, 1960s Counterculture, and Michel Foucault', *Popular Music and Society*, 33.2 (2010) < <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/03007760903142889>>.

¹⁰ Victor Bockris and Gerard Malanga, *Up-tight: The Velvet Underground Story*, Updated Edition (London: Music Sales Limited, 2009), pp.75-76.

¹¹ Ed Vulliamy, 'Why The Velvet Underground's landmark debut album still resonates after 50 years', *The Guardian* (2017) < <https://www.theguardian.com/music/2017/nov/12/velvet-underground-nico-new-york-50-years-john-cale>> [accessed 21 February 2022].

¹² Ibid.

that because of Summer of Love and the promoters' fear of public's reaction the band could not earn the praise that they deserved. Having the courage to sing about the dark side of the humanity was seen by MGM as a possible commercial failure of the record and, as a result, they refused to properly promote it. Harvard also outlined that this situation delayed their worldwide appreciation, receiving it a bit 'too late'.¹³ Watson believes MGM avoided dealing with their record as a consequence of the young generation's reception as this was 'rolling toward the Age of Aquarius'.¹⁴ Under these circumstances, we understand that the band's peculiar musical style was out of the ideal 1967 picture as the society was not yet ready to accept them.

However, over a decade after the album's release, the Velvet Underground started to become relevant in the industry, being considered revolutionary as they paved new ways in rock, punk, new wave, and even electronic music. AllMusic sees the greatness of their debut album through its diversity, stating that 'few rock albums are as important as The Velvet Underground & Nico',¹⁵ whereas Pitchfork describes the record as 'the most dangerous record of 1967'.¹⁶ Today, the album is considered canonical, being certified by the Library of Congress National Recording Registry and ranked Number 13 in Rolling Stone's '500 Greatest Albums of All Time'.¹⁷

In conclusion, despite their musical and commercial unsuccess at the time, The Velvet Underground eventually succeeded in breaking any cultural barrier through their debut album which was a veridical reflection of the vicious society of New York. Moreover, the record proved to be an epitome of musical eminence and stupendous influence in today's rock music through its avant-garde vision, placing the band among the most noteworthy trailblazers in the evolution of the music industry.

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¹³ Joe Harvard, *The Velvet Underground and Nico* (New York: The Continuum International Publishing Group, 2004), p.2.

¹⁴ Steven Watson, *Factory Made: Warhol and the Sixties* (New York: Pantheon Books, 2003), p.315.

¹⁵ Mark Deming, review of 'The Velvet Underground & Nico', *AllMusic* <<https://www.allmusic.com/album/the-velvet-underground-nico-mw0001955423>> [accessed 1 March 2022].

¹⁶ Miles Raymer, review of 'The Velvet Underground & Nico 45th Anniversary [Super Deluxe]', *Pitchfork* (2012) <<https://pitchfork.com/reviews/albums/17129-the-velvet-underground-nico/>> [accessed 1 March 2022].

¹⁷ David Chiu, 'The Velvet Underground's landmark debut turns 45', *CSB News* (2012) <<https://www.cbsnews.com/news/the-velvet-undergrounds-landmark-debut-turns-45/>> [accessed 5 March 2022].

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